

Comparison between Neostigmine Methylsulphate and Clonidine Hydrochloride with Heavy Bupivacaine in Spinal Anesthesia for Elective Abdominal Hysterectomy

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Abstract:

Introduction: Intrathecal neostigmine acts by inhibition of breakdown of acetylcholine. It produces analgesia by increased concentration of acetylcholine in spinal cord. Intrathecal clonidine acts on post synaptic alpha 2 agonist and produces analgesia by inhibition of WDR (wide dynamic range) neurons. In this study we compared effects of clonidine and neostigmine intrathecally for elective abdominal hysterectomy.

Materials and Methods: Total 60 patients posted for elective abdominal hysterectomy divided into two groups. Group N (n=30) received 3 ml of 0.5% heavy bupivacaine with 45 mcg of neostigmine. Group C (n=30) received 3 ml of 0.5% heavy bupivacaine with 45 mcg clonidine. Both groups were compared for onset and duration of sensory and motor blockage, haemodynamic stability and post-operative analgesia.

Results: Time for sensory onset (T10) was faster in group N (1.65±0.66 min) than group C (3.71±1.99 min). Time for onset of motor block was faster in group N (1.74±0.49 min) than group C (4.12±2.46 min). Post-operative analgesia was prolonged in group C (326±11.76 min) than in group N (280±14.61 min). Hypotension, bradycardia and sedation were more seen in group C while nausea and vomiting were more seen in group N.

Conclusion: Intrathecal neostigmine with bupivacaine in elective abdominal hysterectomy provides faster sensory and motor blockade while prolonged post-operative analgesia seen with intrathecal clonidine. Both drugs can safely be used as an adjuvant as an alternative to opioid free spinal analgesia.

Keywords: Intrathecal clonidine, neostigmine, spinal anesthesia, postoperative analgesia.

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Introduction

The prevalence of hysterectomy is 11.35% in India. [1] Muscle relaxation during surgery and post-operative analgesia are two important concerns by anaesthetists in this surgery. Intrathecal neostigmine acts by inhibition of breakdown of acetylcholine, an endogenous neurotransmitter. It produces analgesia by increased concentration of acetylcholine in spinal cord and its action on muscarinic and nicotinic receptors. [2] It does not cause hypotension, sedation, respiratory depression or neurological dysfunction [3]. Intrathecal clonidine acts on postsynaptic alpha 2 agonist which inhibits central transmission of nociceptive stimuli. [4,5] The analgesic effect of clonidine is due to inhibition of wide dynamic range neurons (WDR). High doses of intrathecal clonidine can cause sedation, respiratory depression, hypotension and bradycardia. Therefore we decided to study the effect of clonidine and neostigmine intrathecally for abdominal hysterectomy in terms of

hemodynamic stability, duration of motor and sensory block and post-operative analgesia.

Materials and Methods

This was a prospective randomized controlled trial. Written informed consent was taken for the study and thorough preoperative check-up was done.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Age between 40 to 60 years
- Posted for elective abdominal hysterectomy
- ASA grade I and II

Exclusion Criteria:

- History of allergy to any drug
- Neurological disorder or neuropathy
- Renal impairment
- Liver impairment
- Cardiovascular diseases

Patients posted for elective abdominal hysterectomy were randomized in two groups by odd and even method through computer generated numbers. There were total 60 patients enrolled in this study. Group N (n=30) received injection heavy Bupivacaine (0.5%) 3ml with 45ug neostigmine intrathecally. Group C (n=30) received an injection of heavy Bupivacaine (0.5%) 3ml with 45ug Clonidine intrathecally.

Preloading with ringer lactate solution (10-12 ml/kg) was given intravenously through 20 G IV cannula. In operation theatre standard monitors for ECG, NIBP and Spo2 were applied. Baseline vitals HR, SBP, MAP, DBP and Spo2 were recorded. The patient was positioned in a sitting position with head bent forward. Under all aseptic and antiseptic precautions intervertebral space between L3-L4 was identified and a 25 gauge spinal needle was inserted. After confirming free flow of CSF study drug was given as per her group over 10 to 15 seconds. The patient was placed in supine position immediately after giving the drug. Time for onset of sensory and motor block was recorded. HR, SBP, DBP, MAP,

Spo2 and sedation were monitored every 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 minutes and then every 15 minutes till end of surgery. Onset of sensory block was noted as the time taken to loss of pinprick sensation at T10 level after intrathecal injection.

The level of sensory block was determined by using pinprick by checking every 2 minutes until drug fixation time of 20 minutes. The onset of motor block was checked by Bromage scale. Sedation was assessed by a four-point sedation scale. Time for rescue analgesia noted in both groups. Injection tramadol 50 mg was given intravenously as a rescue analgesia.

Statistical analysis

Comparison of qualitative variables was measured by unpaired chi square test. Comparison of quantitative variables was analysed by independent students 't' test. A p value of 0.05 was taken as level of significance. Data analysis was done by SPSS software version 26.

Observation and Result

Table 1: Demographic Data of the Patients

	GROUP – C (n=30)	GROUP – N (n=30)	P VALUE
Age in years (mean ± SD)	49.6 ± 6.8	44.9 ± 8.5	0.07
Weight in kg (mean ± SD)	61.9 ± 5.5	60.3 ± 7.5	0.47
ASA Grade I/II	13/17	11/19	0.66
Duration of surgery in min (mean ± SD)	125.3 ± 10.4	132.8 ± 12.2	0.05

Table 2: Time for Onset of Motor Blockage (Min)

	Group – C		Group – N		P Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Time for onset of Motor blockage (min)	4.12	2.46	1.74	0.49	<0.001

Table 3: Time for Onset of Sensory Blockade (Min)

Time for onset of Sensory blockade (Min)	Group – C		Group – N		P Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
T10	3.71	1.99	1.65	0.66	<0.001
T4	7.95	1.03	3.66	1.19	<0.001

Table 4: Time of Rescue Analgesia (Min)

	Group - C		Group – N		P Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Time of Rescue analgesia (min)	326	11.76	280	14.61	<0.05

Table 5: Perioperative Changes in Heart Rate (Per Min)

Time	Group - C		Group – N		P Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Baseline	96	9.6	84.5	14.9	0.01
2 min	91.2	9.7	86.5	16.6	0.31
4 min	87.9	9.2	86.2	15.8	0.70
6 min	86.6	7.7	84.1	17.7	0.59
8 min	84.4	9.9	80.3	18.1	0.40
10 min	81.4	8.9	78.6	14.4	0.48
15 min	79.1	10.7	79.5	13.5	0.91
30 min	74.4	10.8	77.8	8.1	0.29

45 min	73.7	12.6	76.5	8.9	0.44
60 min	72.6	12.6	74.2	6.4	0.62
75 min	74.7	12.9	74.6	6.4	0.97
90 min	73.3	10.2	76.1	6.6	0.33
105 min	73.4	9.9	79.3	6.7	0.04
120 min	73.8	8.1	78.1	7.0	0.09
150 min	74.4	7.8	76.3	6.5	0.44

Figure 1:

Table 6: Perioperative Changes in Systolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)

Time	Group - C		Group - N		P Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Baseline	134.4	12.9	138.7	13.8	0.34
2 min	125.6	13.3	135.5	13.8	0.04
4 min	122.2	12.9	133.2	14.4	0.02
6 min	118.4	12.7	128.8	19.3	0.06
8 min	117.9	10.8	125.8	14.4	0.07
10 min	113.6	14.8	122.5	17.8	0.11
15 min	109.4	12.1	121.6	15.2	0.01
30 min	104.7	12.3	121.3	16.1	0.001
45 min	101.6	12.1	121.8	15.8	<0.001
60 min	105.7	7.5	121.2	13.6	<0.001
75 min	107.7	8.8	121.5	14.4	0.001
90 min	109.9	7.8	124.1	15.6	0.002
105 min	110.8	8.3	124.5	12.5	<0.001
120 min	110.2	7.4	126.7	17.1	0.001
150 min	109.8	7.8	123.5	16.1	0.003

Figure 2:

Table 7: Perioperative Changes in Diastolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)

Time	Group - C		Group - N		P Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Baseline	84.4	5.1	82.4	6.8	0.33
2 min	82.8	6.4	82.1	6.2	0.75
4 min	78.9	6.9	81.9	7.6	0.22
6 min	77.0	6.3	79.6	6.2	0.22
8 min	76.2	9.3	77.9	6.3	0.52
10 min	74.4	9.3	77.0	9.5	0.42
15 min	72.0	9.5	75.2	6.1	0.24
30 min	67.8	9.7	73.9	7.6	0.04
45 min	67.4	6.9	75.7	7.2	0.001
60 min	68.0	8.6	75.5	7.2	0.008
75 min	69.6	7.8	77.1	8.3	0.008
90 min	70.8	6.4	77.7	10.2	0.02
105 min	71.7	5.3	79.2	9.6	0.006
120 min	71.1	5.5	79.4	7.7	0.001
150 min	70.7	6.4	77.3	10.4	0.03

Figure 3:

Table 8: Perioperative Changes in Mean Arterial Pressure (mmHg)

Time	Group – C		Group - N		P Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Baseline	96.4	9.8	98.6	10.4	0.52
2 min	93.1	7.3	96.7	10.0	0.23
4 min	89.4	8.3	94.6	9.3	0.08
6 min	87.1	11.0	91.9	11.3	0.20
8 min	88.3	10.1	87.4	11.7	0.82
10 min	85.6	10.4	86.9	11.1	0.72
15 min	83.0	11.5	87.3	10.3	0.24
30 min	79.3	10.9	92.1	13.5	0.04
45 min	78.0	10.1	91.2	12.8	0.01
60 min	77.2	10.8	90.4	11.5	0.001
75 min	79.8	12.0	91.0	12.6	0.01
90 min	81.1	9.2	91.0	12.6	0.01
105 min	82.1	8.7	94.0	13.0	0.04
120 min	82.4	7.7	93.0	13.8	0.008
150 min	81.5	9.1	90.9	12.6	0.01

Figure 4:

Table 9: Perioperative Complications

Complication	Group C	Group N
Nausea	1	8
Vomiting	1	2
Hypotension	2	-
Bradycardia	3	-
Sedation	4	-

Demographic variables like age, weight and ASA grading and duration of surgery were comparable in group C and group N (Table 1). Time for sensory onset (T10 sensory) was 3.71 ± 1.99 mins in group C and 1.65 ± 0.66 mins in group N. Time for onset of motor blockage in our study in Group C was 4.12 ± 2.46 mins and in Group N was 1.74 ± 49 mins. Postoperative analgesia was prolonged in group C (326 ± 11.76 mins) than in group N (280 ± 14.61 mins). Patients were hemodynamically stable throughout surgery in group N. In group C there was statistically significant fall in SBP, MAP, DBP from baseline as compared to group N after 15 min. There was fall in HR in group C compared to group N. Hypotension, bradycardia and sedation were more common in group C while nausea and vomiting were more common in group N. Respiratory depression was not seen in any group.

Discussion

This study was designed to compare the intrathecal effects of two non-opioid drugs Neostigmine and Clonidine. The main aims of this study was to compare sensory and motor block characteristics, hemodynamic stability and postoperative analgesia.

Neostigmine, an anticholinesterase agent proven sufficient for alleviating somatic pain and helpful for prolonging postoperative analgesia by activating descending pain inhibitory pathways [6]. Clonidine has been widely used by oral, parenteral, epidural, spinal routes for postoperative analgesia. Intrathecal clonidine produces analgesia by activation of postsynaptic alpha 2 receptors in substantia gelatinosa. [7]

In our study mean sensory onset time (T10) in Group C was 3.71 ± 1.99 mins and Group N was 1.65 ± 0.66 mins which is similar to the study done by N. Yoganarasimha et al [8]. In their study mean sensory onset time in Group BC was 160 ± 2 secs and in Group BN was 98 ± 15 secs

Time for onset of motor blockage in our study in Group C was 4.12 ± 2.46 mins and in Group N was 1.74 ± 49 mins which was similar to the study done by Mamta Goda and Nilesh Bhatnagar- [9]. In their study, the onset of motor blockage was 3.58 ± 0.89 mins in Group BC and 2.77 ± 0.68 mins in group BN. The time for rescue analgesia was 326 ± 11.76 mins in Group C and 280 ± 14.61 mins in Group N which was similar to study done by N.

Yoganarasimha et al [8] and Mamta goda et al [9]. In their study time for rescue analgesia in Group BC was longer than Group BN.

There was no significant difference in mean pulse rate of both groups in our study. There was no significant difference in blood pressure of both groups till 15 minutes, then after various time intervals the fall in Blood pressure was statistically significant. There were more cases of bradycardia and hypotension seen in group C than in group N [15]. Intraoperative blood pressure was well maintained in Group N than Group C which was similar to the study done by Solaiappan B et al [10], Bhar D et al [11] and Uma Maheshwararao et al [12].

Intrathecal neostigmine produces nausea and vomiting due to rostral spread of neostigmine to brainstem site [13]. Hyperbaric local anesthetic drugs prevent rostral spread. In our study nausea and vomiting was more common in Group N (8 patients) than Group C (2 patients).

This finding was similar to a study done by Shaikh Sohail Ahmed et al [14]. No respiratory depression or sedation was seen in both the groups in our study [8].

Conclusion

Intrathecal Neostigmine with bupivacaine in elective abdominal hysterectomy provides faster sensory and motor blockade while prolonged post-operative analgesia seen with intrathecal clonidine. Both intrathecal neostigmine and clonidine in low dose can be used as an adjuvant to bupivacaine as an alternative to commonly used opioids in spinal anesthesia without serious adverse effects.

Bibliography

- Rout D, Sinha A, Palo SK, Kanungo S, Pati S. Prevalence and determinants of hysterectomy in India. 2023 Sep 4; 13(1); 14569. doi: 10.1038/s41598-023-41863-2.
- Fishman SM, Ballantine JC, Rathmell JP, editors. Bonica's Management of Pain. 4th ed Philadelphia; Wolters Kluwer/Lippincott Williams and Wilkins; 2009. p.1448.
- Lauretti GR, Reis MP, Prado WA, Klamt JG. Dose-response study of intrathecal morphine versus intrathecal neostigmine, their combination, or placebo for postoperative analgesia in patients undergoing anterior and posterior vaginoplasty. *Anesth Analg*. 1996 Jun; 82(6):1182-7. doi: 10.1097/00000539-199606000-00014. PMID: 8638788.
- Strebel S, Gurzeler JA, Schneider MC, Aeschbach A, Kindler CH. Small-dose intrathecal clonidine and isobaric bupivacaine for orthopedic surgery: a dose-response study. *Anesth Analg*. 2004 Oct; 99(4):1231-1238. doi: 10.1023/B:ANE.0000133580.54026.65. PMID: 153 85382.
- Eisenach JC, De Kock M, Klimscha W. alpha (2)-adrenergic agonists for regional anesthesia. A clinical review of clonidine (1984-1995). *Anesthesiology*. 1996 Sep; 85(3):655-74. doi: 10.1097/00000542-199609000-00026. PMID: 8853097.
- Ho KM, Ismail H, Lee KC, Branch R. Use of intrathecal neostigmine as an adjunct to other spinal medications in perioperative and peripartum analgesia: a meta-analysis. *Anaesth Intensive Care*. 2005 Feb; 33(1):41-53. doi: 10.1177/0310057X0503300107. PMID: 159576 90.
- Tryba M, Gehling M. Clonidine--a potent analgesic adjuvant. *Curr Opin Anaesthesiol*. 2002 Oct; 15(5):511-7. doi: 10.1097/00001503-200210000-00007. PMID: 17019247.
- Yoganarasimha N, Raghavendra T, Amitha S, Shridhar K, Radha M. A comparative study between intrathecal clonidine and neostigmine with intrathecal bupivacaine for lower abdominal surgeries. *Indian J Anaesth*. 2014 Jan; 58(1):43-7. doi: 10.4103/0019-5049.126794. PMID: 24700898; PMCID: PMC3968650.
- Goda M, Bhatnagar N. Intrathecal Bupivacaine with Neostigmine versus Clonidine as an Adjuvants in Lower Abdominal Surgeries. *Indian Journal of Anesthesia and Analgesia*. 2018; 5(6):963-8.
- Solaiappan B, Jeevarathnam R. Comparative Study of Intrathecal Neostigmine and Clonidine. *Journal of Evolution of Medical and Dental Sciences*. 2016 Jul 16; 5(57):3917-25.
- M Santhi Sree & N Krishna Veni. A comparative study between intrathecal bupivacaine with clonidine vs bupivacaine with neostigmine for Vaginal Hysterectomies: A Randomised Double Blinded Study. *Indian J Anesth Analg*. 2018; 5 (7): 1210-14.
- Rao VU, Shankar. Efficacy of intrathecal bupivacaine alone with neostigmine and clonidine in lower abdominal surgeries- a comparative study. *EAS EAS J Anesthesiol Crit Care*. 2019; 1(4):78-82.
- Hood DD, Eisenach JC, Tuttle R. Phase I safety assessment of intrathecal neostigmine methylsulfate in humans. *Anesthesiology*. 1995 Feb; 82(2):331-43. doi: 10.1097/00000542-199502000-00003. PMID: 7856891.
- Shaikh SA, Chandak D, Rangrez A an Ab R, Rauf MAurRA. Effect of adding intrathecal dexmedetomidine, neostigmine and clonidine as an adjuvant to hyperbaric bupivacaine for elective Caesarean section. *E J Mole Clin Medi*. 2022;9(4):
- Mehta M, Sharma T, Miyajiwala F, Chandini D. Intrathecal clonidine versus intrathecal

midazolam with hyperbaric bupivacaine for
post-operative analgesia in abdominal
hysterectomy: A randomized study

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<https://doi.org/10.53730/ijhs.v6nS1.5707>.